

2 A 2-adic density lemma

Lemma 2.1 (Decreasing 2-adic density). *Let m be an odd integer and let $r = \nu_2(3m + 1)$ be the largest exponent of 2 dividing $3m + 1$. Then the odd integers m satisfying $\nu_2(3m + 1) = r$ form a single residue class modulo 2^{r+1} , and their density among the odd integers is*

$$\delta_r = \frac{1}{2^r}.$$

Density justification. The congruence $3m + 1 \equiv 0 \pmod{2^r}$ has a unique solution $m \equiv a \pmod{2^r}$ because $\gcd(3, 2^r) = 1$. This describes those integers m for which $\nu_2(3m + 1) \geq r$.

To isolate those with *exactly* $\nu_2(3m + 1) = r$ we consider the congruence modulo 2^{r+1} . Write $m = a + t2^r$ with $t = 0, 1$ and use $3a + 1 = 2^r c$ with c odd. Then

$$3m + 1 = 3(a + t2^r) + 1 = 2^r(c + 3t).$$

If $t = 0$, then $c + 3t = c$ is odd, hence $\nu_2(3m + 1) = r$. If $t = 1$, then $c + 3$ is even, hence $\nu_2(3m + 1) \geq r + 1$. Therefore the integers with $\nu_2(3m + 1) = r$ form exactly one residue class modulo 2^{r+1} .

Since the density of a single class modulo 2^{r+1} in \mathbb{Z} is $1/2^{r+1}$ and the density of the odd integers is $1/2$, the relative density among the odds is

$$\frac{1/2^{r+1}}{1/2} = \frac{1}{2^r}.$$

□

Corollary 2.2 (Spacing between successive occurrences). *Let d_r be the number of odd integers strictly between two consecutive odd integers m satisfying $\nu_2(3m + 1) = r$. Then*

$$d_r = 2^r - 1.$$

Proof. The solutions form an arithmetic progression with step 2^{r+1} in \mathbb{Z} . Between two odd integers separated by 2^{r+1} there are exactly $2^r - 1$ odd integers. □

Observation 2.3. *The lemma shows that each lower row of the table represents a sparser and sparser set of odd integers. For finite levels r the density is positive, but in the limit $r \rightarrow \infty$ it vanishes. This reveals the hierarchical and 2-adic nature of the Collatz dynamics: at each level of divisibility by 2, the density of odd integers reaching it is halved, which in the graphical representation appears as increasing spacing and an increasingly empty table.*

3 4-adic reduction and compressed representation by families

The previous section explains why the lower rows of Figure 1 are increasingly sparse. We now use the same 2-adic datum to group odd integers into *families* determined by a common *even closure node*, i.e. the last even number in the odd–even step of Collatz.

Let n be an odd integer and let

$$A = \frac{3n + 1}{2^{\nu_2(3n+1)-1}}$$

be the *last even number* before the orbit returns to an odd one. If

$$3n + 1 = 2^r q \quad (q \text{ odd}),$$

then $A = 2q$, so $A/2 = q$ is exactly the next odd value. In particular, every such A satisfies $A \equiv 2 \pmod{4}$, and in fact $A \equiv 2$ or $10 \pmod{12}$.

All odd integers m producing the same A satisfy

$$3m + 1 = A \cdot 2^s \quad (s \geq 0),$$

because dividing $3m + 1$ by 2^{s-1} yields A as the last even number. For m to be an integer we need $A2^s \equiv 1 \pmod{3}$. Since $2 \equiv -1 \pmod{3}$, there are two cases:

- If $A \equiv 1 \pmod{3}$ (i.e. $A \equiv 10 \pmod{12}$), then $2^s \equiv 1 \pmod{3}$, so s is even. Writing $s = 2k$,

$$m = \frac{A \cdot 2^{2k} - 1}{3} = \frac{A \cdot 4^k - 1}{3}, \quad k = 0, 1, 2, \dots$$

- If $A \equiv 2 \pmod{3}$ (i.e. $A \equiv 2 \pmod{12}$), then $A2^s \equiv 1 \pmod{3}$ forces s odd. Writing $s = 2k + 1$,

$$m = \frac{A \cdot 2^{2k+1} - 1}{3} = \frac{2A \cdot 4^k - 1}{3}, \quad k = 0, 1, 2, \dots$$

Definition 3.1 (Family associated with a last even number). *Let A be a last even number in the odd trajectory, with $A \equiv 2, 10 \pmod{12}$. Define the family associated with A by*

$$\mathcal{F}_A = \begin{cases} \left\{ \frac{A \cdot 4^k - 1}{3} : k \geq 0 \right\}, & \text{if } A \equiv 10 \pmod{12}, \\ \left\{ \frac{2A \cdot 4^k - 1}{3} : k \geq 0 \right\}, & \text{if } A \equiv 2 \pmod{12}. \end{cases}$$

Proposition 3.2 (Disjoint partition into families). *Every odd integer n belongs to a unique family \mathcal{F}_A . Moreover, if $A \neq B$ then $\mathcal{F}_A \cap \mathcal{F}_B = \emptyset$.*

Proof. For a given odd n , the factorization $3n + 1 = 2^r q$ with q odd is unique; hence the derived value $A = (3n + 1)/2^{r-1} = 2q$ is unique. Therefore n cannot satisfy $3n + 1 = A2^s$ and $3n + 1 = B2^t$ with $A \neq B$, which proves disjointness and uniqueness of membership. \square

Proposition 3.3 (Uniqueness of the $4 \rightarrow 2 \rightarrow 1$ cycle in the family graph). *Consider the directed graph whose nodes are families \mathcal{F}_A , and where we draw an edge $\mathcal{F}_A \rightarrow \mathcal{F}_B$ if the next odd obtained from a representative of \mathcal{F}_A belongs to \mathcal{F}_B . Then the only family admitting a self-loop is \mathcal{F}_2 .*

Proof. If $A = 2$, then the next odd is $A/2 = 1$, and $1 \in \mathcal{F}_2$, so $\mathcal{F}_2 \rightarrow \mathcal{F}_2$. If $A > 2$, the next odd is $A/2 = q$ with q odd, and q belongs to a family determined by its own closure node, which is not A in general. Hence \mathcal{F}_A cannot map to itself. \square

Proposition 3.4 (Modular classes of even closure nodes). *If A is an even closure node, i.e.*

$$A = \frac{3n + 1}{2^{\nu_2(3n+1)-1}},$$

then necessarily

$$A \equiv 2 \text{ or } 10 \pmod{12}.$$

Proof. For odd n , one has $3n + 1 \equiv 4$ or $10 \pmod{12}$. Dividing by powers of 2 until the last even value yields a number congruent to 2 or 10 $\pmod{12}$. \square

Conjecture 3.5 (Global attraction to the family \mathcal{F}_2). *In the reduced structure by families \mathcal{F}_A defined from even closure nodes, the family*

$$\mathcal{F}_2 = \{1, 5, 21, 85, \dots\}$$

acts as a global attractor. That is, every orbit of the reduced graph starting from a family \mathcal{F}_A with $A > 2$ is conjectured to reach \mathcal{F}_2 in finitely many steps.

Comment (Computational evidence). *Conjecture 3.5 has been verified computationally for all even closure nodes $A \leq 10^6$ with $A \equiv 2, 10 \pmod{12}$. In this range, no alternative directed cycles were detected in the reduced structure, and all orbits reached $A = 2$ (equivalently, \mathcal{F}_2). Details are given in Appendix C.*

Figure 2: Reduced structure by 4-adic families. The family \mathcal{F}_2 is the only one admitting a self-loop. Computational verification up to $A \leq 10^6$ supports the conjecture that all families reach \mathcal{F}_2 .

Conclusion

This study does not address a complete proof of the Collatz conjecture, but provides a structural description of its odd–even dynamics based on two complementary ingredients.

First, the 2-adic density lemma identifies a hierarchy of levels determined by $\nu_2(3n + 1)$ and explains the pattern of increasing gaps observed in the tabular representation of odd trajectories.

Second, the even closure node groups odd integers into 4-adic families \mathcal{F}_A and yields a reduced family graph in which \mathcal{F}_2 is the unique family admitting a self-loop, corresponding to the classical cycle $4 \rightarrow 2 \rightarrow 1$.

Global attraction to \mathcal{F}_2 is formulated as a conjecture. In support of it, Appendix C reports computational verification up to $A \leq 10^6$, where no alternative directed cycles were detected and all orbits reached $A = 2$.

A Connection with the structure theorem for (d, g, h) -maps

A.1 The Kontorovich–Sinai framework

Kontorovich and Sinai introduce a general framework for Collatz-type transformations, called (d, g, h) -maps, defined by

$$T(x) = \frac{gx + h(gx)}{d^{\nu_d(gx+h(gx))}},$$

where $d, g \in \mathbb{N}$ and $h : \mathbb{Z} \rightarrow \mathbb{Z}$ is periodic modulo d . The exponent $\nu_d(y)$ denotes the highest power of d dividing y .

A.2 Collatz as a particular case

The classical Collatz map corresponds to $d = 2$, $g = 3$ and $h(x) = 1$:

$$T(n) = \frac{3n + 1}{2^{\nu_2(3n+1)}}.$$

This is the map underlying the present work, where $\nu_2(3n + 1)$ determines the even-tail length and the even closure node $A = (3n + 1)/2^{\nu_2(3n+1)-1}$.

A.3 Drift and local expansion

Kontorovich and Sinai define the *drift*

$$\mu = \log g - \frac{d}{d-1} \log d.$$

For $(d, g) = (2, 3)$ one gets $\mu < 0$, indicating average contraction.

In the present framework, an odd-even segment has local factor

$$G = 3^j 2^{-(n-j)},$$

and $\log G < 0$ similarly characterises contraction at the segment level.

B Transition from classes $4n+3$ to $4n+1$ in the simplified dynamics

B.1 Motivation

For the simplified Collatz map

$$T(n) = \begin{cases} n/2, & n \text{ even,} \\ (3n + 1)/2, & n \text{ odd,} \end{cases}$$

every odd class $n \equiv 3 \pmod{4}$ eventually reaches the class $n \equiv 1 \pmod{4}$.

B.2 Sketch of the modular mechanism

Let $n = 4k + 3$. Then

$$T(4k + 3) = \frac{3(4k + 3) + 1}{2} = 6k + 5,$$

and $6k + 5 \equiv 1 \pmod{4}$ iff k is even. If k is odd, writing $k = 2t + 1$ yields a new parameter $t < k$, and iterating reduces the parameter until a $4n + 1$ is reached. Hence permanence in $4n + 3$ is finite.

Corollary B.1 (Finite permanence of the class $4n + 3$). *Under $T(n) = (3n + 1)/2$, every trajectory starting at an odd integer $n \equiv 3 \pmod{4}$ enters the class $n \equiv 1 \pmod{4}$ in finitely many steps.*

C Computational verification up to even closure nodes $A \leq 10^6$

This appendix reports the verification, for all even closure nodes $A \leq 10^6$ with $A \equiv 2$ or $10 \pmod{12}$, that the reduced dynamics does not exhibit alternative directed cycles in that range and that every orbit reaches the fixed node $A = 2$.

C.1 Reduced map on even closure nodes

Given an even closure node $A \equiv 2, 10 \pmod{12}$, the next visible odd is $q = A/2$. Define the *reduced successor* of A as the new even closure node obtained after applying $3q + 1$ and dividing by powers of 2 until the last even is reached:

$$T(A) = \frac{3(A/2) + 1}{2^{\nu_2(3(A/2)+1)-1}} = \frac{3A + 2}{2^{\nu_2(3A+2)-2}}, \quad A \equiv 2, 10 \pmod{12}. \quad (1)$$

The node $A = 2$ satisfies $T(2) = 2$.

C.2 Verification algorithm

We scanned the set

$$\mathcal{A}_{10^6} = \{A \in 2\mathbb{N} : A \leq 10^6, A \equiv 2 \text{ or } 10 \pmod{12}\}.$$

For each $A \in \mathcal{A}_{10^6}$ we iterated the map (1), recording visited states until one of the following occurred:

1. the orbit reaches $A = 2$;
2. a state $A \neq 2$ repeats (which would detect an alternative directed cycle).

In the explored range, event (1) always occurred and event (2) never did.

C.3 Results summary

The set \mathcal{A}_{10^6} has cardinality

$$|\mathcal{A}_{10^6}| = 166\,667.$$

In the explored range:

- **Convergence:** for every $A \in \mathcal{A}_{10^6}$ there exists $t \geq 0$ such that $T^t(A) = 2$.
- **No alternative cycles detected:** no directed cycle different from the self-loop at $A = 2$ was found.
- **Transient lengths:** letting $\tau(A)$ be the smallest t such that $T^t(A) = 2$, we obtained

$$\max_{A \in \mathcal{A}_{10^6}} \tau(A) = 166 \quad (\text{attained at } A = 820\,022), \quad \mathbb{E}[\tau] = 43.63.$$

Percentiles:

$$P_{50} = 41, \quad P_{75} = 58, \quad P_{90} = 72, \quad P_{95} = 81, \quad P_{99} = 101.$$

C.4 Interpretation

This verification is not a proof of global convergence for all A , but provides quantified and reproducible evidence that, up to $A \leq 10^6$, the only cyclic behaviour of the reduced dynamics is the self-loop at $A = 2$.

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